

THE ROLE OF MARKETING IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF TOURISM ACTIVITIES

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***Abstract.** This article discusses the issues of innovative development of the tourism sector, the reasons and factors hindering the increase in the efficiency of their activities, and also offers suggestions for solving existing problems.*

***Keywords:** economy, tourism, private business, tourist activity, tourist resources, marketing, tourist industry, tourist product.*

***Аннотация:** В данной статье рассмотрены вопросы инновационного развития сферы туризма, причины и факторы, препятствующие повышению эффективности их деятельности, а также даны предложения по решению существующих проблем.*

***Ключевые слова:** экономика, туризм, частный бизнес, туристская деятельность, туристские ресурсы, маркетинг, турбизнес, турпродукт.*

INTRODUCTION. Currently, an important condition for such a rapid development of the economic sector is the accelerated introduction of modern innovative technologies, that is, successful activity is impossible without innovation. Rapidly developing all spheres of state and public life of the country require close support of ongoing reforms based on modern innovative ideas, developments and technologies that ensure a quick and high-quality breakthrough of the country into the ranks of world civilization leaders.

The development of the economy of Uzbekistan is certainly connected with the development of the tourism industry, which is a social and priority area, the development of which affects the economy of both the state and the global economy. More than 10 percent of the world's gross domestic product is provided by the tourism industry, and about 75-80 percent is generated by the service sector. However, despite such rapid development, there are many problems associated with this activity in the sphere, which indicates a significant lag behind the economically developed countries of the world.

Our Republic has a huge resource potential for the development of the sphere. First of all, the presence of over 7.4 thousand objects of material cultural heritage of different eras and civilizations, including the historical centers of Samarkand, Bukhara, Khiva and Shakhrisabz included in the UNESCO World Heritage List, testifies to the capabilities of our country. The country is rich in 11 national nature parks, state reserves, 37 theaters, 106 museums, 187 recreation and cultural parks, as well as many other tourism facilities.

The presence of ancient attractions, mosques, mausoleums, madrassas, as well as many unspoiled corners of nature, medical centers, and many resources allow you to develop many types of tourism. World-famous historical monuments, modern cities, the unique nature of Uzbekistan, the unique national cuisine, as well as the unsurpassed hospitality of our people attract travel lovers. Thanks to this, a breakthrough in obtaining foreign exchange earnings from tourism activities and replenishing the country's budgets is possible in the country. In other words, the tourism industry produces a tourist product that is in demand both in the foreign and domestic markets. The main task of the tourism industry is to create a high-quality and popular tourist product.

MATERIALS AND METHODS. In the process of writing the article, textbooks, regulatory acts of the Republic of Uzbekistan, statistical data of the State Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan were used, as well as the general analysis method was implemented.

DEGREE OF STUDY. Issues related to innovation activity and its development were considered in the works of domestic and foreign scientists such as: J.Schumpeter, A.Chicherin, Y. Gribov, F.Valent, L.Vodachek, O.Vodachkov, M. Hucek, G.Mensch, A.Karimova and others. [4,5,6,7,8,9,10,11,12,13,17,18]

THE MAIN PART. Innovation activity focuses on the results of scientific research, as well as experimental developments.

The term "*innovation*" in its modern sense, the Austrian scientist J. Schumpeter was the first to apply it. He emphasized that innovation is a significant change in the function of what is produced, consisting in a new combination and commercialization of all new combinations based on the use of new materials and components, the introduction of new processes, the opening of new markets, as well as the introduction of new organizational forms. [4,18,19]

To produce, according to Schumpeter, is to combine the things and forces available in our sphere. To produce something different or otherwise is to create other combinations of these things and forces. The central place in his theory is occupied by the entrepreneur - innovator as the creator of new products, new markets, new technologies. According to Y. According to Schumpeter, innovation is the main source of profit: "... profit is essentially the result of performing new combinations", "... development there is no profit, without profit there is no development " [5].

A similar definition is given by L. Vodachek and O. Vodachkova [6]. In their opinion, innovation is "a targeted change in the functioning of the enterprise as a system, which can be expressed in a quantitative and qualitative transformation in any area of the enterprise's activity." Similar is the view of M. Hucek [7,19], who interprets innovations as: "... changes in technology, organization, economy, as well as in the social life of the enterprise". P. N. Zavlin, A. A. Ipatov and A. S. Kulagin [8,17] by innovation (innovation) mean an object introduced into production as a result of the conducted research. a scientific study or discovery that is qualitatively different from its previous counterpart. Innovation is characterized by a higher

technological level, new consumer qualities of the product or services compared to the previous product.

After studying the works of scientists (J. Schumper, F. Valenta, M. Hucek, P. N. Zavlin, A.A. Ipatov, L.Vodachek, O.Vodachkov, A.S. Kulagin, O.V. Smorudova) we came to the conclusion that on the basis of the conducted research, scientists considered innovations as the transformation of a system using new materials, new equipment, technologies, the introduction of new processes in the field of production activities, that is, the creation of a new consumer product, the quality of which was much higher than the above ones. However, the scientists did not reveal the essence of innovations in the service sector (tourism). In our opinion, an innovatively developed field of activity should be engaged not only in the production and supply of goods, but also in the provision of high-quality services.

Today, the development of the tourism industry is considered as one of the most important areas. Based on international experience, many regulatory acts have been reviewed and adopted in the country. For example, in January of this year, important regulations for the tourism sector were adopted. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On additional measures for accelerated development of tourism in the Republic of Uzbekistan" [1], as well as the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures for accelerated development of the tourism industry [2]". These regulations define the main strategic directions for the development of the tourism sector. In particular, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan approved the Concept of development of the tourism sector in the period up to 2025 [3] with the annual adoption of a plan of specific measures to implement the Concept.

Based on the above-mentioned regulations, currently the main directions of state policy in the field of tourism are:

- ❖ development of this sphere as a strategic branch of the country's economy;
- ❖ ensuring the rights of citizens to rest, freedom of movement and other rights when traveling;

- ❖ rational use and preservation of tourist resources;
- ❖ improvement of the regulatory framework;
- ❖ creating the necessary conditions for the development of domestic tourism, including organizing tourism and excursions for children, youth, the elderly, as well as persons with disabilities and low-income segments of the population within the framework of social tourism development;
- ❖ attracting investment and creating favorable conditions for investment in the tourism sector;
- ❖ development of public-private partnership in this area;
- ❖ organization and development of scientific research;
- ❖ training, retraining and advanced training of personnel;
- ❖ development of international cooperation;
- ❖ improving the image of the Republic of Uzbekistan as a country attractive for tourism;
- ❖ providing state support to the subjects of the tourism sector in promoting their national tourist product in the tourist markets;
- ❖ stimulating the introduction of advanced innovative and information and communication technologies;
- ❖ stimulating the development of tourist zones and tourist clusters, etc.

Fig. 3. Number of companies engaged in tourism activities activity

As of October 1, 2019, 1,381 travel companies are successfully operating in the country. Statistics on the export of tourist services since the beginning of 2017 amounted to more than 694 million US dollars, these figures increased to 1,557 million US dollars by the end of 2017.[19] In 2018, it grew to \$ 1.4 billion. The export of tourist services in 2019 amounted to \$ 854.5 million. Compared to the same period last year (\$666.8 million), the export of tourist services increased by 28 percent [8,9,15,16,].

As statistics show, a lot of work has been done in the tourism sector. But, despite this, there are still many unresolved problems, the existence of which is an obstacle to the development of activities. These include:

- lack of an effective financial and credit support mechanism;
- lack of financial mechanisms of the innovation and investment support system;
- lack of a simplified credit system (high interest rate);
- restrictions on preferential taxation;
- lack of a financial institution, support and development of tourism.
- the solution of these problems based on the development of state regulation and

support for the activities of the tourism sector will make it possible to make the most effective use of the existing tourist potential of the country.

- in other words, the tourism industry produces a tourist product that is in demand both in the foreign and domestic markets.

Based on the above, we consider it necessary to eliminate the factors that are obstacles in the strategic plan for the formation of financial resources in order to ensure that tourism enterprises are competitive.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS. Summing up, we can conclude that the existing problems hinder the innovative development of the tourism sector, which affects the receipt of additional funds in the country's budget revenues.

The creation of a marketing company engaged in marketing research in the tourism sector will lead to the solution of the above problems, that is, it will be possible to meet the needs of tourists, ensure replenishment of budgets at all levels,

attract foreign currency to the region, solve socio-economic problems, and increase the level of employment of the population.

In our opinion, the main activity of a marketing company should consist in carrying out the following activities:

- survey of tourists (identification of requests for the quality of services provided, price, needs);
- identification of problems faced by tourists when arriving in the country;
- preferences and interests of tourists in the country;
- identify the most important trends in the tourism sector in the country;
- survey and survey of tourism business entities;
- conducting master classes on training qualified personnel, conducting successful work for companies.

These activities should be carried out jointly. Interviewing potential tourists at destination markets abroad, analyzing competitors' offers, and identifying destination markets involves high financial costs in the former cases, while in the latter cases information is unavailable. Therefore, these functions should be performed at the expense of budget funds and with the participation of government representatives.

Marketing activities should be carried out at the levels of regional and central tourism management bodies, tourist businesses and public organizations, which should act on the basis of standards established by the state bodies of the republic. The activities of all structures must be coordinated by the Uzbektourism Tourism Agency of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

In conclusion, tourism is an essential part of the entire country's economy. The implementation of the proposed form of public-private partnership will contribute to the development of tourism organizations, enhance the introduction of new competitive tourist products, increase the efficiency of their activities, create additional jobs, stimulate the formation of new organizations, increase tax revenues, and increase the welfare of the population.

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